

Donor Properties of Pyridine and Quinoline Carboxylic Acids : Pyridine and Quinoline Carboxylato Complexes of Chromium(III)

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A few complexes with pyridine and quinoline carboxylic acids of general composition CrL_3 or $Cr(LH)_3$ (where LH and LH_2 represent monobasic and dibasic bidentate ligand respectively) have been prepared and characterized on the basis of magnetic moments, i.r. and visible spectral measurements and elemental analyses. Magnetic moments show three unpaired electrons per chromium for each complex. The complexes have two d-d transitions in the visible region. The i.r. spectra and molar conductance values of the complexes indicate the formation of neutral chelates.

DURING recent years there has been an increased interest in coordination complexes of chromium (III)^{1,2}. A few complexes of chromium(III) with pyridine carboxylic acids (picolinic, nicotinic and lutidinic acids) and quinoline carboxylic acids (quinoline-2-carboxylic and quinoline-8-carboxylic acids) of the composition CrL_3 or $Cr(LH)_3$ are reported in this paper where LH and LH_2 represent the monobasic and dibasic bidentate ligand respectively. These complexes are obtained by refluxing alcoholic solution of $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ and the pyridine/quinoline carboxylic acid in appropriate quantity. Tris (lutidinato) chromium (III) has, however, been synthesized by interacting $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ with excess lutidinic acid in aqueous medium.

Experimental

Materials used :

Pyridine carboxylic^{3,4} and quinoline carboxylic acids^{5,6} were prepared according to the literature. Their trivial names are used, together with the common abbreviations: (a) Pyridine-2-carboxylic acid (picolinic acid), abbreviated as picH; (b) Pyridine-3-carboxylic acid (nicotinic acid), abbreviated as nicH; (c) Pyridine-2, 6-dicarboxylic acid (lutidinic acid), abbreviated as lutH₂; (d) quinoline-2-carboxylic acid (quinaldinic acid), abbreviated as 2-qH; (e) quinoline-8-carboxylic acid, abbreviated as 8-qH.

Chemically pure $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (U.S.S.R.) was used.

Preparation of the complexes :

(i) $Cr(pic)_3$. Clear alcoholic solution of $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.26g ; 1 mmole) and alcoholic solution of

picolinic acid (0.43g ; 3.5 mmoles) were mixed and refluxed on sand bath for one hour when rose-red crystalline compound precipitated. This was filtered, washed several times with alcohol and finally dried over $CaCl_2$. The complex is insoluble in water but fairly soluble in alcohol.

(ii) $Cr(nic)_3$. The green compound was obtained when $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.26g ; 1 mmole) and nicotinic acid (0.43g ; 3.5 mmoles) in alcohol was refluxed on sand bath for short periods.

This is highly soluble in water, acetone etc.

(iii) $Cr(lutH)_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$. Saturated aqueous solution of $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.26g ; 1 mmole) was mixed with hot, saturated aqueous solution of lutidinic acid (0.58g ; 3.5 mmoles) and the mixture was concentrated on water bath. On concentrating and cooling excess lutidinic acid separated. It was then removed and the clear filtrate was further concentrated and cooled to room temperature to yield pink crystals of $Cr(lutH)_3 \cdot 1.5H_2O$. A second crop of complex was obtained by further concentrating the mother liquor. The solid obtained was washed with hot water and dried over $CaCl_2$.

The complex is highly soluble in water but fairly soluble in alcohol, acetone etc.

(iv) $Cr(2-q)_3$. The pale green tris complex was obtained when alcoholic solution of $CrCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (0.26g ; 1 mmole) and quinaldinic acid (0.60g ; 3.5 mmoles) were refluxed on sand bath for short period.

The complex is not fairly soluble in most of the common organic solvents.

(v) $Cr(8-q)_3$. The deep green tris (quinoline-8-

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carboxylato) chromium(III) was prepared by adopting the same method as used to prepare Cr(2-q)₃, except that quinoline-8-carboxylic acid was used in place of quinaldinic acid.

The complex is insoluble in most of the common organic solvents.

The analytical data are presented in Table 1.

The molar conductances, electronic absorption spectra, magnetic susceptibilities and elemental

for lutidinato complex is different. The asymmetric stretch of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ at 1665 cm^{-1} indicates the coordination of carboxyl group with the metal ion but there is no band observed close to 1700 cm^{-1} which could be assigned to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of carboxyl group. This may be due to strong hydrogen bonding interactions between free carboxyl group and water or with another free carboxyl group of the adjacent molecules¹⁰. The weak vibration at 870 cm^{-1} and medium intensity vibration at 910 cm^{-1} are probably due to rocking mode of water molecules¹¹. The

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND OTHER CHARACTERIZATION DATA OF THE COMPLEXES.

Complex	% Cr		Analytical data % N		% H ₂ O		Magnetic moment (B.M.) at 298°K	I.R. data (cm ⁻¹) COO (asym) stretch		Absorption spectra λ_{max} , 10Dq (nm) (cm ⁻¹)	Molar conductance (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹) at 29° (methanol)
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found		Complex.	Ligand		
1. Cr(pic) ₃	12.40	12.30	10.05	9.90	—	—	3.75	1670	1710	540 18520	26.2
2. Cr(nic) ₃	12.40	12.20	10.05	9.80	—	—	3.80	1665	1695	570 17540	63.5
3. Cr(lutH) ₃ 1.5H ₂ O	9.60	9.80	7.18	7.35	4.62	4.73	3.75	1665	1690	550 18180	60.0
4. Cr(2-q) ₃	9.20	9.30	7.40	7.20	—	—	3.80	1657	—	545* 18350	—
5. Cr(8-q) ₃	9.20	9.25	7.40	7.30	—	—	3.70	1636	—	560* 17860	—
6. Cr(H ₂ O) ₆ ³⁺ *Mull spectra	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	575 17400	—

analysis were done as described earlier¹. The i.r. spectra (KBr) were obtained from Central Drug Research Institute (Lucknow, India).

Results and Discussion

All the complexes listed in Table I are stable under ordinary conditions. The complexes were found to be paramagnetic at room temperature (25°) as expected for chromium(III) ion. The magnetic moments for the complexes are slightly below than calculated from 'spin-only' formula but not without reason⁷.

The complexes have two d-d transitions in the visible region (Table I). The bands around $17,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to transition derived from ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$ and bands around $22,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been assigned to transition derived from ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}$. The Dq. values obtained for these complexes are compared with that of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$ in octahedral field. It is observed that the Dq. values of these complexes are much greater than that of $\text{Cr}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{3+}$, thus indicating greater coordinating ability of these ligands. The nicotonic acid, on the otherhand, is the weakest donor in this series, being slightly stronger than water.

The complexes are not fairly soluble in common organic solvents such as acetone, chloroform, nitrobenzene etc. The molar conductances have been reported (Table 1) for those which are soluble. The data give, as expected, non-electrolytic values.

I. R. spectra indicate the absence of free carboxylic acid group in the pyridine monocarboxylato complexes. The relative lowering of 40 cm^{-1} and 30 cm^{-1} of asymmetric stretch of carbonyl group in picolinato and nicotinato derivative of chromium(III) with respect to free reagents⁹, indicate that carboxyl group is bound with the metal ion. The situation

wagging and twisting modes of water molecules which occur at lower frequency cannot be detected due to the restriction of the i.r. measurement. The i.r. bands for tris (quinoline-2-carboxylato) chromium(III) and tris (quinoline-8-carboxylato) chromium(III) also indicate the coordination of carboxyl group with the metal ion. Further the position of asymmetric stretch of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ group in these complexes clearly indicates that the metal ion forms a covalent bond to the carboxyl-oxygen and this bond changes with the degree of covalency in metal-oxygen bond¹²⁻¹⁴.

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